

Expression of metaphor in artistic translation

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Annotation: This article focuses on the metaphor of the medium of fiction and the coverage of its use in literature. We know that the most important weapon in fiction is the word. How effective and understandable it is to be delivered through the means of artistic representation. Metaphor is widely used not only in the Nazi way of fiction, but also in prose. Through this article, I would like to prove this term through examples, citing the use of it in fiction and the goals of the writer or poet in their works.

Key words: Metaphor, auxiliary, additions, subordinate word, ruler word, synecdoche, literature, translation, research.

The science of Uzbek linguistics has achieved tremendous achievements over the past period. This is also shown by the fact that problems with all levels of language are put in the middle and the scientific research being carried out. In order to understand the content of any text, it is enough to know the lexicon and grammar of the language, in order to perceive the content of an artistic text, it is also necessary to know the specific linguistic-poetic laws of an artistic text. It is known that in addition to its original meaning, words also mean portable. When words are used in a portable sense, it not only refers to subject-phenomena, but also functions to describe those objects and phenomena. Portable meaning arises at the base of the literal meaning of words in a language. Colloquial words are used in all styles except scientific and formal. The portable meaning of words is only realizable in the context

Metaphors are manifested in one way or another in all manifestations of poetic works as a means of expressing the poet's thoughts figuratively to the extent that they affect the reader. In poetic texts, depending on what the subject is described in the poem, depending on the purpose of the writer himself, the linguistic means serve to perform an important methodological task. Such tools are also considered relevant as means of expression-image in works on methodology, as an aesthetic phenomenon that ensures the originality of an artistic text, provokes staining. If this type of tool is

used appropriately in the text, the image chosen by the author in the work will be reflected in the eyes of the reader or listener in artistic paints. The metaphors used in the artistic text affect the feelings of the reader with their tactile nature, delighting him, putting him in different mental states. In addition metaphors save a person from expressing their thoughts through long sentences using the tools available in language. With the help of metaphors, the thoughts of the writer are reflected in a short and clear, simple and figurative way. The study of artistic texts is important in individualizing the author's speech and character speech of Uzbek creators, identifying their worthy contributions to enriching the treasure of the Uzbek literary language-image, linguopoetic means, lexical-phraseological resources, units of the people-in the creation of portraits, various natural landscapes and poetic images.

Metaphor is a literary device that evokes a comparison between two seemingly dissimilar objects. In this case, the subject of thing A provides the creation of the word of the governor. Through this method of equation, metaphor helps to explain an unknown concept by colorfully associating it with a particular concept; concretizing abstract ideas; and it greatly serves to make incomprehensible concepts understandable

In fiction, portable (Trops) at the lexical level are extremely important, they are the most active tools in expressing artistic content. Especially among migrations, metaphor as an important and widely used tool arose on the basis of the results of artistic visions in our language. The use of a previously existing name in a language for a new meaning on the basis of a certain similarity does not perform only a simple nomination task, but also serves as an influence (expressive) on the listener, and expands the expressive capabilities of the language. In connection with the understanding of metaphor as one of the important mechanisms of human thinking, in particular, figurative thinking, and not just a moving or artistic tool, from the middle of the XIX century, along with literary studies, many fields of science, such as linguistics, philosophy, logic, psychology, semiotics, have also studied within their interests. Even in Uzbek literary studies, the understanding of metaphor only as a street came to an end, and its role in fiction, in artistic thinking, the defining feature of creative style began to be studied from the 80s of the last centuries. Since the 70s in Uzbek linguistics, a number of works have come to the Square, which are devoted to the study of meaningfulness and portability of words. In this regard, the linguist M.It

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023

should be noted separately the services of mirtozhiev. Studies have also been created devoted to studying the metaphor from the point of view of linguistics, the place it occupies in the poetry of a particular creator. In these studies, metaphor has been given a place among the tools that generate Street MA, and the focus is on identifying aspects of metaphor that differ from other tools in the system of tools that give rise to Street MA. G. Kabuljonova study metaphor and its linguistic nature. In Uzbek, metaphor sees lexical meaning as one of the path of progress, and is assessed as an ocean-based type of migration. Sh.Rahmatulayev.

To conclude through metaphor two related concepts that are not similar or related to each other are linked, unexpected readings are made in order to attract the attention of the reader, the writer of abstract and incomprehensible cases delivers to the reader through exactly the same method. Many writers in fiction sometimes use it to color the thoughts they want to express. The reason is, the works draw the reader to themselves with their artistic readings. Especially when animating animals or inanimate objects, the use of such artistic means is required. Like other artistic imagery tools, metaphor is a very powerful weapon. Because, through the metaphor you put in, you create a view between the mind of the reader and your strong image, and with that you freely imagine the hero of the reader and the world in which he lives, making every thought interesting, vital you can lay the groundwork for what you can do.

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